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WITH INTERNATIONAL PARTICIPATION

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**Section „Biology“ – Union of Scientists in Bulgaria
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LANDSCAPE ECOLOGY

SUBMARINE LANDSCAPE DIVERSITY OF VARNA COASTAL ZONE (BULGARIAN BLACK SEA): PRESENT-DAY ECOLOGICAL ISSUES AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE MARINE SPATIAL PLANNING

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Abstract

Having originated in the former USSR, the notion of the submarine landscape as a seabed geo-ecocomplex is a concept rapidly gaining popularity nowadays. Pursuant to these ideas, the landscape comprises a group of inter-linked, hierarchically organized subsystems, implying for the taxonomic subordination of the underwater units.

Aim: To identify, systemize hierarchically and represent graphically the seabed complexes at Varna coastal zone, to evaluate their nature conservation importance and to assess the current ecological issues of the cited sector.

Data and Methods: Several data sources concerning the underwater landscape components (e.g. seabed substrates, seafloor geomorphology, dominant benthic biota etc.) were analyzed in GIS.

Results: The submarine landscape diversity of the study site comprises 43 kinds united in 7 genera, 5 types and 2 classes. The greatest impact upon the seabed is observed at the resorts and port areas of Varna Municipality.

Discussion and Conclusions: The current marine use often runs counter to the conservation value of the benthic landscapes, with the Aladzha bank being a rather alarming example. Recommendations targeted at optimization of the marine spatial planning are accompanied with a map of the suggested marine use types.

Keywords: marine landscape studies, benthic landscape units, marine NATURA 2000, Aladzha bank, ICZM, GIS

Introduction

The scientific concept viewing the landscape as a natural complex is an idea that is widely adopted in some East European countries, former USSR states and Russia in particular. According to this notion, the landscape is a spatially defined part of the geographic sphere, a dynamic geo-ecosystem that is genetically uniform, has a definite resource potential and is influenced to a certain extent by anthropogenic activity [1]. Since the 1990's of the XX century, this theoretic view of what the landscape represents is rapidly gaining popularity in the Nordic countries [e.g. 2, 3]. Furthermore, the scientific

concepts emphasize the spatial delimitation of the landscape complexes and the hierarchic ranking of the landscape units [4].

Despite having emerged initially as a terrestrial interdisciplinary field bridging over geography, ecology, social sciences etc., over the course of the XX century the landscape sciences were subsequently adopted in oceanography as an approach for complex investigation of marine basins, whose primary purpose is to provide detailed maps of the benthic environment in help of the economic sectors involving the use of the marine natural resources [5]. The underwater landscape is again perceived as a natural complex, combining the principal geocomponents and factors of the benthic environment (e.g. loose and solid sublittoral substrates, seafloor geomorphology, hydrodynamic regime, depth zonation and related light availability etc.), with the contiguous group of floristic, epi- and infaunal organisms that inhabit the seabed [3, 5, 6].

Description of the study area

The investigated seabed sector stretches between cape Ekrene on the north and cape Galata on the south, falling entirely within the boundaries of the Varna coastal zone, which occupies the foothills of the Franga and Avren plateaus (Fig. 1). It has a total planimetric area of roughly 6 693.5 ha and an off-the-coastline width varying between 2.4 and 8.3 km, while the maximum depths reach values of approximately 21-23 m. The sublittoral substrates are presented by loose sediments (e.g. varying in grain size sand, sandy silts and silts), additionally diversified by solid lithologic varieties dominated by sandstones and conglomerates. The underwater relief is mostly of accumulative or structural-accumulative type, thereby dominated by corresponding landforms, e.g. wave-formed sandy bars, accumulative and structural-accumulative slopes, structural-accumulative terraces, structural depressions, accumulative platforms etc. The seafloor topography is also characterized by the presence of abrasive and other azonal morphologic features, e.g. plantigrade slopes of structural or landslide-collapse genesis, structural-abrasive benches, rocky banks, geogenic reefs etc. The spatial occurrence and distribution of the macrobenthic biological communities demonstrate a strong relation to the seabed lithologic varieties, grain size of the loose deposits, intensity of the wave-induced sediment transport, hydrodynamic activity and depths [7]. The psammophilous infauna is mostly dominated by clams belonging to the families *Mesodesmatidae* (*Donacilla cornea*), *Donacidae* (*Donax trunculus*), *Corbulidae* (*Lentidium mediterraneum*), *Veneridae* (*Chamelea gallina*), *Tellinidae* (*Tellina tenuis*), while the sectors with shelly sand and gravels are populated by species from the *Mytilidae* (*Gibbomodiola adriatica*), *Veneridae* (*Gouldia minima*) etc. In addition, the deeper seabed areas with sandy silts and silts are inhabited by representatives of *Macluridae* (*Spisula subtruncata*), *Semelidae* (*Abra alba*), *Cardiidae* (*Parvicardium exiguum*) etc., as well as by thalassinidean shrimps (e.g. *Upogebia pusilla*). The epilithic fauna in the shallow zone is normally dominated by *Mytilidae* mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Mytilaster lineatus*), gradually turning into monodominant communities of *Mytilus galloprovincialis* with the increase of depth

[8]. Finally, the dominant macroalgal flora is presented mainly by annual communities of green and red algae, as well as by *Cystoseira* sp. at the rocky seabed areas with clean waters, decreased turbidity and improved light availability [7].

Fig. 1. Location and spatial extent of the investigated seabed sector

Data and Methods

Several graphic and descriptive data sources were used in the process of the GIS-aided submarine spatial analysis for identification and interpretation of the geo-components forming the study area's vertical landscape structure. These include the ESRI shape files on the seabed lithology, bathymetric contours, scanned maps of the seafloor geomorphology etc., as well as limited narrative and point GIS data concerning the dominant macrobenthic communities (Table 1).

Table 1. List of the initial data used in the process of the GIS-aided submarine landscape analysis

Name of the initial data set/source/hard-copy map	Data format	Spatial resolution/ minimum mapping unit/map scale	Data source
Seabed lithology of the Varna coastal zone	ESRI shape file (vector)	1:5,000	Department “ <i>Coastal zone dynamics</i> ” at IO-BAS
Bathymetric contours	ESRI shape file (vector)	2 m	Department “ <i>Coastal zone dynamics</i> ” at IO-BAS
8 GIS layers on the marine use types at the study area	ESRI shape file (vector)	N/A	Department “ <i>Biology and ecology of the sea</i> ” at IO-BAS
Point data on dominant macrobenthic biological communities	ESRI shape file (vector)	N/A	Department “ <i>Biology and ecology of the sea</i> ” at IO-BAS
Boundaries of the „Varna-Beloslav Lake” NATURA 2000 site (Birds Directive)	ESRI shape file (vector)	1:100,000	www.natura2000.moew.government.bg
Boundaries of the “Aladzha bank” NATURA 2000 site (Habitats Directive)	ESRI shape file (vector)	1:5,000	www.natura2000.moew.government.bg
5 scanned seabed morphologic maps of the Varna coastal zone	tiff (raster)	1:10,000	Keremedchiev, 2013 (<i>personal archive</i>)
General spatial plan of the Varna Municipality	tiff (raster)	1:25,000	www.varna.bg
Locations of aquaculture farms and fishing nets at the Varna coastal zone	Excel tables	N/A	www.iara.government.bg
Zones prohibited for commercial fishing in 2014 [9]	Pdf document with string data on geographic coordinates	N/A	www.iara.government.bg

All graphic data were integrated, processed and analyzed in Arc GIS 9.3.1 (Fig. 2). The second step of the analysis was the taxonomic grouping of the identified landscape units into the hierarchic categories, applying a four-level classification system developed by the author for the entire central sector of the Bulgarian Black Sea coastal zone [10]. The main aspects of the cited categorization criteria are summarized in Table 2. The final stage of the GIS-aided analysis was an assessment of the current and projected marine use at the Varna coastal zone, alongside with the major ecological issues emanating from its weaknesses, with a stress on the planned spatial development inside the designated marine NATURA 2000 sites. This was

done primarily by reviewing the latest version of the General Spatial Municipal Plan (Table 1). The recommendations for optimization of the marine spatial planning were addressed and visualized as a digital map of the suggested marine use types.

Fig. 2. Generalized flowchart of the procedures carried out in Arc GIS 9.3.1 software environment

Table 2. Main features of the applied landscape hierarchic categorization criteria (Kotsev [10])

Hierarchic category	Conditionally natural submarine landscapes	Anthropogenic submarine landscapes
Landscape class	Macrogeomorphologic criteria (macro-relief of the seabed, e.g. <i>Landscape of the submarine coastal slope</i>)	Introduced for better hierarchic correlation with the classification scheme of the conditionally natural submarine landscapes; one single class, namely <i>Anthropogenic submarine landscapes</i>
Landscape type	Intensity of the wave-induced sediment transport and intensity of the geomorphodynamic processes within the submarine coastal slope	Level of alteration of the seabed complex (e.g. <i>Landscape with significant to complete transformation of the natural complex</i>)
Landscape genus	Trends in the geomorphodynamic processes (e.g. abrasion or accumulation) and distribution depths of the landscape units	Trends in the geomorphodynamic processes (e.g. abrasion or accumulation) as a result of the anthropogenic intervention (often irreversible), or used as a category heading for a group of entirely artificial seabed elements
Landscape kind	An underwater complex formed by relatively uniform seabed landforms, sublittoral substrate types and associated dominant macrobenthic biological communities, found at particular depths and constructing altogether the submarine landscape's vertical structure	Indication of the particular anthropogenic landscape kinds that often coincide with given marine use categories, e.g. <i>port areas, navigable canals, stationary pound nets</i> etc.

Results

Present-day seabed landscape diversity of the Varna coastal zone. The submarine landscape diversity of the investigated sublittoral region consists of 43 kinds, hierarchically united in 7 genera, 5 types and 2 classes (Fig. 3). The seabed landscape pattern is dominated by accumulative and structural-accumulative complexes, found in the weakly active and inactive (in geomorphodynamic sense) zones, distributed at depths greater than 10 m. The submarine anthropogenic landscape units are concentrated within the relatively shallow near-shore areas contiguous to the recreational, harbor and port zones of the Varna Municipality, as well as at the coastline sections with hydrotechnical structures present, occupying approximately 13.6% of the investigated underwater sector (Table 3).

Table 3. Relative coverage (in % of the studied seabed sector) of the identified submarine landscape genera

Name of the submarine landscape genus	Relative coverage (in % of the study area)
Slope, abrasive-structural & abrasive-landslide-collapse landscapes at depths 0-10 m	2.6
Accumulative (including structural-accumulative) landscapes at depths 0-10 m and rarely reaching 15 m	3
Abrasive (including structural-abrasive) landscapes at depths 5-15 m and rarely reaching 20 m	0.6
Accumulative (including structural-accumulative) landscapes at depths 5-20 m and rarely reaching 30 m	12
Accumulative (including structural-accumulative) landscapes at depths 10-30 m and rarely reaching 42 m	68.2
Accumulative anthropogenic landscapes	5.1
Landscapes formed entirely by anthropogenic activities	8.5

Morphologic seabed features of nature conservation importance. Undoubtedly, the Aladzha bank represents the most important benthic entity when discussing marine nature conservation at the Varna coastal zone. With its area of approximately 522 ha, it is a representative example of the biotope “**Infra- and circalittoral rock overgrown by mussels *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Mytilaster lineatus***” – a variety of 1170 (Reefs) NATURA 2000 habitat type. Established as a protected site of the cited European ecological network, the Aladzha bank is important for the geographic coherence and connectivity between the northern and southern reefs in the Bulgarian sector of the Black Sea [11].

SEABED LANDSCAPE COMPLEXES AT THE STUDIED SUBLITTORAL AREA

Fig. 3. Map of the contemporary submarine landscapes at the Varna coastal zone

NB: A-B – landscape classes, I-IV – landscape types, 1-7 – landscape genera, 1.1-7.3 – landscape kinds

A. Landscapes of the submarine coastal slope. I. Landscapes of the geomorphodynamically active zone. 1.

Slope, abrasive-structural & abrasive-landslide-collapse landscapes at depths 0-10m: 1.1. Abrasive landscapes at structural slopes, with coarse sand and infauna domin. by Donacidae, Veneridae etc. clams,

developed at depths of 3-7 m; 1.2. Abrasive landscapes at structural slopes, with medium sand and infauna domin. by *Donacidae*, *Corbulidae*, *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae*, *Arcidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 3-7 m; 1.3. Abrasive landscapes at the landslide & landslide-collapse plantigrade slopes, with medium sand and infauna domin. by *Donacidae*, *Corbulidae*, *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae*, *Arcidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 2-10 m; 1.4. Abrasive landscapes at the landslide-structural-plantigrade slopes of conglomerates overgrown by *Mytilidae* mussels and *Cystoseira* brown algae, developed at depths of 0-10 m; 1.5. Landscapes of the geogenic reefs and rocky banks of sandstones overgrown by *Mytilidae* mussels and green & red annual algal communities, developed at depths of 0-10 m; **2. Accumulative (incl. structural-accumulative) landscapes at depths of 0-10 m and rarely reaching 15 m:** 2.1. Accumulative forebeach landscapes, with unsorted coarse & medium sand and infauna domin. by *Mesodesmatidae*, *Donacidae* etc. clams and *Polychaeta* worms, developed at depths 0-7 m; 2.2. Accumulative landscapes at wave-formed bars, with medium sand and infauna domin. by *Mesodesmatidae*, *Donacidae* etc. clams and *Polychaeta* worms, developed at depths of 0-7 m; 2.3. Accumulative landscapes at wave-formed bars, with coarse sand and infauna domin. by *Donacidae*, *Veneridae* etc. clams and *Polychaeta* worms, developed at depths of 3-7 m; 2.4. Accumulative landscapes at wave-formed bars, with medium sand and infauna domin. by *Donacidae*, *Corbulidae*, *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae*, *Arcidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 3-7 m; 2.5. Accumulative landscapes at wave-formed bars, with fine sand and infauna domin. by *Corbulidae*, *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae*, *Arcidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 0-10 m; 2.6. Slope-accumulative landscapes, with medium sand and infauna domin. by *Donacidae*, *Corbulidae*, *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae*, *Arcidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 3-7 m; 2.7. Slope-accumulative landscapes, with fine sand and infauna domin. by *Corbulidae*, *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae*, *Arcidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 0-15 m; 2.8. Geostructurally formed accumulative landscapes, with fine sand and infauna domin. by *Corbulidae*, *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae*, *Arcidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 0-15 m. **II. Landscapes of the weakly active zone.** **3. Abrasive (incl. structural-abrasive) landscapes at depths of 5-15 m and rarely reaching 20 m:** 3.1. Abrasive landscapes at structural terraces, with medium sand and infauna domin. by *Donacidae*, *Corbulidae*, *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae*, *Arcidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 5-10 m; 3.2. Abrasive landscapes at structural terraces, with unsorted medium & fine sand and infauna domin. by *Corbulidae*, *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae*, *Arcidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 5-10 m; 3.3. Landscapes of the geogenic reefs and rocky banks of sandstones overgrown by *Mytilidae* mussels and green & red annual algal communities, developed at depths of 5-10 m; 3.4. Landscapes of the rocky banks of sandstones overgrown by *Mytilidae* mussels, sponges, hydrozoans etc., developed at depths of 10-20 m. **4. Accumulative (incl. structural-accumulative) landscapes at depths of 5-20 m and rarely reaching 30 m:** 4.1. Geostructurally formed slope-accumulative landscapes, with coarse sand and infauna domin. by *Donacidae*, *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 7-15 m; 4.2. Geostructurally formed slope-accumulative landscapes, with coarse sand and infauna domin. by *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae* etc. clams and *Polychaeta* worms, developed at depths 8-20m; 4.3. Geostructurally formed slope-accumulative landscapes, with medium (rarely heterogeneous unsorted) sand and infauna domin. by *Donacidae*, *Corbulidae*, *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae*, *Arcidae* etc. clams, developed at depths 5-15 m; 4.4. Geostructurally formed slope-accumulative landscapes, with unsorted medium & fine sand and infauna domin. by *Corbulidae*, *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae*, *Arcidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 8-15 m; 4.5. Geostructurally formed slope-accumulative landscapes, with sandy silt and burrows of thalassinidean shrimps or infauna domin. by *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 10-20 m; 4.6. Accumulative landscapes at structural terraces, with unsorted medium & fine sand and infauna domin. by *Corbulidae*, *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae*, *Arcidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 8-12 m. **III. Landscapes of the inactive deep-water zone.** **5. Accumulative (incl. structural-accumulative) landscapes at depths of 10-30 m and rarely reaching 42 m:** 5.1. Slope-accumulative & platform-accumulative landscapes with unsorted

coarse & fine sand and infauna domin. by *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae* etc. clams and *Polychaeta* worms, developed at depths of 15-20 m; 5.2. Slope-accumulative & platform-accumulative landscapes, with medium sand and infauna domin. by *Donacidae*, *Corbulidae*, *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae*, *Arcidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 10-15 m; 5.3. Slope-accumulative & platform-accumulative landscapes, with fine sand and infauna domin. by *Corbulidae*, *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae*, *Arcidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 10-15 m; 5.4. Slope-accumulative & platform-accumulative landscapes, with sandy silt and burrows of thalassinidean shrimps or infauna domin. by *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 10-20 m; 5.5. Slope-accumulative & platform-accumulative landscapes, with silt and infauna domin. by *Veneridae*, *Macruridae*, *Semelidae*, *Cardiidae* etc. clams and *Polychaeta* worms, developed at depths of 10-30 m; 5.6. Geostrurally formed accumulative landscapes at structural terraces, with coarse sand and infauna domin. by *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae* etc. clams and *Polychaeta* worms, developed at depths of 12-20 m; 5.7. Geostrurally formed accumulative landscapes at structural slopes & structural depressions, with unsorted coarse & medium sand and infauna domin. by *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae* etc. clams and *Polychaeta* worms, developed at depths of 12-20 m; 5.8. Geostrurally formed accumulative landscapes at structural slopes & structural depressions, with unsorted medium & fine sand and infauna domin. by *Corbulidae*, *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae*, *Arcidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 12-15 m; 5.9. Geostrurally formed accumulative landscapes at structural slopes & structural depressions, with sandy silt and burrows of thalassinidean shrimps or infauna domin. by *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae* etc. clams, developed at depths of 13-20 m; 5.10. Geostrurally formed accumulative landscapes at structural slopes & structural depressions, with silt and infauna domin. by *Veneridae*, *Macruridae*, *Semelidae*, *Cardiidae* etc. clams and *Polychaeta* worms, developed at depths of 20-25 m; 5.11. Landscapes of the structural bars, with coarse sand and infauna domin. by *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae* etc. clams and *Polychaeta* worms, developed at depths of 12-20 m; 5.12. Landscapes of the structural bars, with sandy silt and burrows of thalassinidean shrimps or infauna domin. by *Veneridae*, *Tellinidae* etc. clams, developed at depths 12-20m; 5.13. Landscapes of the rocky banks of conglomerates overgrown by *Mytilidae* mussels and *Cystoseira* brown algae, developed at depths 10-15 m; 5.14. Landscapes of the rocky banks of sandstones overgrown by *Mytilidae* mussels and green & red annual algal communities, developed at depths of 10-12 m; 5.15. Landscapes of the geogenic reefs and rocky banks of sandstones overgrown by *Mytilidae* mussels, sponges, hydrozoans etc., developed at depths of 12-20 m. **B. Anthropogenic submarine landscapes.** **IV. Landscapes with significant to full modification of the seabed substrates and the associated macrobenthic biological communities.** **6. Accumulative anthropogenic landscapes:** 6.1. Accumulative landscapes in the entry-angle and wave-shadow zones near hydrotechnical structures; 6.2. Port areas. **7. Landscapes with significant to complete transformation of the natural complex:** 7.1. Navigable canals; 7.2. Stationary pound nets; 7.3. Aquaculture installations

Present-day ecological and nature conservation issues at the Varna coastal zone. The study area is well-known for being among the most technogenically transformed sectors along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast, with many negative consequences for the marine environment. Among others, these include:

- Inflow of industrial, chemical and domestic waste, as well as deposition of litter from the land-based resources, leading to a deteriorated state of the marine coastal waters [8];
- Technogenic pressure exerted upon the coastal zone, manifested through erroneously planned, excessive concentration of hydrotechnical structures, which results in sealing, smothering and siltation of the seabed, with main negative consequences being the ongoing physical loss and physical damage of the benthic biotopes [12];

- Direct impacts of recreation upon the marine coastal environment in the summer months, e.g. physical trampling of the soft-bottom mediolittoral (pseudolittoral) habitats at areas with sandy beaches [10];
- Decreased solid runoff from the coastal erosive ravines alongside with the deteriorated nourishment of the accumulative seabed sectors, causing shortage of loose seafloor substrates and eventually leading to seabed conversion at certain sites [13];
- Illegal trawling practicing, resulting in physical damage of the soft-bottom benthic biotopes [14];
- Intensified traffic of marine vessels with related noise and pollution.

Marine spatial planning at the Varna coastal zone - nature conservation vs. current and projected development. The performed GIS-based analysis of the Varna Municipality General Spatial Plan reveals that the current and projected marine use often runs counter to the conservation value of certain seabed sectors, with Aladzha bank being the most disturbing example. Due to the exhausted recreational capacity of the “Golden Sands” maritime resort, the graphic appendices of the cited document foresee the construction of several artificial islands inside the “Aladzha bank” NATURA 2000 site, four of which lying partially or entirely on top of the geogenic reef that is the primary habitat of nature conservation interest and thereby the main reason for designation of the protected area (Fig. 4). Another identified conflict represent the current boundaries of the “Varna-Beloslav Lake” NATURA 2000 site, established in accordance with the Birds Directive. The protected area’s spatial extent includes the two navigable canals connecting the Varna Bay with the homonymous lake, as well as a small section of the aquatory adjacent to Port Varna-East (Fig. 5). Results from the regular monitoring campaigns carried out by IO-BAS regarding the quality of the coastal waters confirm that the cited area is in deteriorated ecological state, although a slight improvement was registered in 2013 in comparison to the preceding year [15]. Thus, its inclusion in the European ecological network raises many questions concerning the hardly attainable long-term improvement of the marine environment in Varna Bay and also, to a certain extent, compromises the effectiveness of NATURA 2000 in the Bulgarian sector of the Black Sea.

Recommended marine use at the study area. The recommendations targeted at improvement of the marine spatial planning are based on a complex analysis of the available data sets enlisted in Table 1. Despite being backed by similar feedbacks expressed in relevant articles and scientific project reports, the suggestions addressed are mainly of wishful nature and reflect private opinions. These recommendations are accompanied with a map of the suggested marine use types. The key features of the proposals addressed are designation of the “Aladzha bank” as a protected area in compliance with the Protected Territories Act of Bulgaria, exclusion from NATURA 2000 of the two navigable canals connecting the Varna Bay with the homonymous lake etc. (Fig. 6).

PROJECTED MARINE SPATIAL DEVELOPMENT AT "GOLDEN SANDS" AND "RIVIERA" RESORTS (source: general spatial plan of Varna Municipality)

Fig. 4. Boundaries of the “Aladzha bank” NATURA 2000 protected site with the identified seabed landscape complexes and projected marine spatial development

"VARNA-BELOSLAV LAKE COMPLEX" NATURA 2000 SITE - CURRENT BOUNDARIES & MARINE ANTHROPOGENIC PRESSURE

Fig. 5. Boundaries of the “Varna-Beloslav Lake” NATURA 2000 protected site and current marine use

Fig. 6. Map of the suggested marine use types within the spatial extent of Varna coastal zone

Discussion and Conclusions

The results of the study reveal that the submarine landscape pattern of the Varna coastal zone is dominated by accumulative and structural-accumulative complexes, formed typically in the weakly active and inactive in geomorphodynamic sense sectors of the submarine coastal slope, which is in agreement with the geomorphologic setup of

the area. The correct interpretations of the seabed lithologic pattern and landforms are recognized as crucial fundamentals of the submarine landscape mapping [3, 6]. However, while the Nordic researchers traditionally apply geologic and geomorphologic criteria in the broad-scale landscape classifications of the seafloor units, this study incorporates them at the lowest taxonomic levels, thereby adopting a “terrestrial” approach that is widespread among the East European scholars, e.g. in Russia, Ukraine and Bulgaria [1, 4].

As a consequence of the decades of long-term technogenic transformations, the anthropogenic landscape units occupy a significant percentage of the investigated seabed sector. This fact poses further implications about the efficiency of the marine spatial planning as an element of the integrated coastal zone management (ICZM) at the Varna coastal zone, whose current level of consistency with the landscape specifics of the region is highly dissatisfactory. Yet, the General Spatial Plan of the Varna Municipality seldom render an account to the poor ecological state of the marine environment or the nature conservation importance of certain seabed features, with the projected construction inside the “Aladzha bank” NATURA 2000 site being an alarming example. Nevertheless, the suggested marine use targeted at improvement of the ICZM, despite being consistent with the specifics of the submarine landscape pattern, reflects mainly the author’s opinion upon the subject.

Due to the poor spatial resolution, certain imperfections characterize the geo-data used, which consequently reflected upon the level of confidence of the results obtained, with GIS layers on the dominant macrobenthic communities being the weakest component of the submarine landscape analysis. Nevertheless, the applied seascape-based approach represents an innovative method for studying the benthic environment.

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